

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GHOSE****FIRST NAME: SOUMITA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows

Key concepts:

1. Introduction (EUCLID 2024, 3-72)
2. Foundational concepts of essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-14)
3. Writing in American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism and how to avoid it (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Writing Styles (EUCLID 2024, 40-56)
6. Corrections and feedback to submitted papers (EUCLID, 65-71)

FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D course pack for period one is a guideline document for the fundamentals of academic paper writing. This document provides a detailed understanding of various aspects of academic writing, such as essay writing principles, use of punctuations, writing in American vs. British English, plagiarism and the rules and ethics of the same, style guide and fundamentals of the Chicago style, Latin abbreviations and expressions commonly used in academic writing, and lastly examples of corrections done to response papers. The document uses relevant examples and explanations to understand these key concepts quickly. It provides a comprehensive guideline for the students to use as a foundation for starting their writing journey. This response paper summarizes five key ideas from this document and includes my reflections as a student, researcher, and healthcare manager on how the skills and knowledge gained from this coursework will benefit my overall growth as an academic writer.

2) FOUNDATIONAL CONCEPTS OF ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the academic writing course highlights foundational concepts of writing academic essays. While acknowledging that essay writing is not linear (EUCLID

2024, 7), the training material begins by elaborating a stepwise approach to writing an academic essay. In this, the importance of starting early on without procrastinating on the topic is emphasized, along with the suggestion that developing a fair understanding of the topic of the essay through a review of the literature is highly recommended. The stepwise approach also focuses on introducing the main topic or the question in the essay and corroborating the same with the analysis and answers. It is thus essential to draft an initial structure after adequate research on the topic of interest and to organize one's ideas about how to write about the topic in an essay. Formulating a good reading list is critical to the quality of the final essay as it determines the length and breadth of the topic covered by the writer and how well the questions are answered through relevant information and theories found in the literature review (EUCLID 2024, 8-9). It is thus helpful to populate a reading list curated to the topic of exploration. At the same time, the role of creative and free thinking cannot be emphasized enough as it broadens the original idea (EUCLID 2024, 9) and makes the essay argumentative, balanced, and insightful. The step of writing the essay provides directives around the structure of the essay, which needs to be divided into an introduction, the body of the essay, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10).

Each section, as described in the structure, needs to follow a logical orientation; for example, the introduction of the essay provides a summary of the topic and goes from general to specific (EUCLID 2024, 10). The essay's body essentially covers the main topics, written in paragraphs. It answers the questions and develops the discussion around the topic, often using relevant examples, quotes, and theories from the reviewed literature. The conclusion section of the essay moves from specific conclusions to general statements (EUCLID 2024, 10); however, it is advised not to introduce any new topic or concept in the conclusion section. Upon completing the writing, the next step is to reference the critical essay for protection against plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 11). Careful essay editing immediately after a few days of the first draft enhances the document with new perspectives, closing the gaps in arguments and analysis, language revisions, punctuations, spelling, and so forth (EUCLID 2024, 12). In conclusion, a few critical considerations while writing an essay are to introduce the main topic clearly and early on in the document, concentrate on the aspects that one is trying to argue on instead of covering the entire spectrum of the topic, be concise and clear on the topic in hand, avoid unnecessary quotes, make fair and severe arguments on the topic and lastly avoid plagiarizing either the concept or the statements from other sources (EUCLID 2024, 12).

Essay writing is done for different purposes. I have written policies and academic documents as a healthcare manager and researcher for many years. However, the orientation on a structured methodology of writing an essay provides valuable insights and makes me reflect on the process I have been following. While I resonate with the value of a well-done literature review, I also ponder the importance of retaining the originality or novelty of the author's views while working on an academic piece. Through personal experience, I have observed that a literature review may restrict one's mind about the topic; therefore, it may be better to write down the raw ideas in a first draft before starting the literature review. Making the introduction general to specific is an exciting insight as I often do not pay close attention to this when I write policies or research papers (EUCLID 2024, 10). I can see the value in gradually engaging the reader in one's document while

slowly introducing the concept and its technicality stepwise. I can see transferable knowledge from this section that will be valuable in my industry practice as a policy writer.

3) WRITING IN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

The next topic of the academic writing course is writing styles in American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32). American English is currently the most widely used in the world (EUCLID 2024, 25). This is attributable to a few factors, such as the population of the US being predominantly English speakers, the influence of the US economy, the existence of a large publishing industry in the US and the impact of mass media, the adoption of American culture on the language and habits of people and the international politico-economic position of the country (EUCLID 2024, 25). While both American and British English hail from the same background of world English, they do have distinctive differences, some of which are described below (EUCLID 2024, 25-27).

a) Difference in pronunciation, despite the exact spelling

For the precise spelling of words, Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) pronounce them differently. For example, the word dance is pronounced differently in SAE and SBE.

b) Difference in spelling, despite the same pronunciation

Similar to the point above, words with the same pronunciation are spelled differently between the SAE and SBE. For example, color in SAE and colour in SBE are pronounced the same (Grammarly 2021).

c) Similar spelling and pronunciation

There are words in SAE and SBE that are essentially the same term but are spelled similarly but not the same. For example, a raise in SAE and a rise in SBE both mean an increase in wages.

d) Use of Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation

In SAE, commas and periods are placed inside the quotation mark, while the exact opposite is practiced in SBE.

e) Usage with Large Collective Nouns

In SAE, significant collective nouns are used as singular, whereas in SBE, they are considered plural. For example, “The Beatles is playing tonight” would be written as “The Beatles are playing tonight” in SBE.

f) Other differences

Various other differences between American and British English stem from cultural, religious, regional, and political underpinnings (EUCLID 2024, 30-31). In addition, things such as dates and punctuation after salutations are written differently in SAE and SBE.

As a student raised in India, I attended a school where English was a second language, and it was only in college that the teaching medium was English. While reading this chapter in the coursework, I realized how English is written and taught differently in different parts of the world. I faced a certain amount of difficulty in understanding the examples of the SAE and SBE, as I couldn’t recognize which one was which. This also made me realize that in my part of the world, we do not always pay attention to this level of detail in professional writing. Academic writing, however, is different from industry writing, and I found the concepts helpful more as a researcher than a health policy manager. Furthermore, I found the idea of equality vocabulary quite fascinating. I was unaware that the choice of words in colloquial may have different inherent connotations.

4) PLAGIARISM AND HOW TO AVOID IT

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2024, 34). This section of the coursework highlights the importance of understanding plagiarism, how to cite and paraphrase, and the use of footnotes in essay writing. It is also noted that any original work being done by someone else, if claimed to be of one’s own, without crediting the original author, is considered plagiarism. Plagiarism is considered an academic offense due to its unethical and unfair approach (EUCLID 2024, 34). This section of the course material gives guidelines on how to avoid plagiarism in academic work by ensuring proper citation of sources of information, data, and theories. The following types of citations are discussed:

- a) In-text citations (EUCLID 2024, 35)
- b) Quotations (EUCLID 2024, 35)
- c) Paraphrases (EUCLID 2024, 36)

While in-text citations and quotations are more direct ways of citing sources, paraphrases are a more complex means of citing someone else’s work written in the other person’s language. It is recommended that paraphrasing is done in a language that is

distinctively different from the original writer's but without losing or altering the meaning of what's being written. The chapter also talks about items that do not require citation, such as when information is used from a common source of knowledge (EUCLID 2024, 37). Another way of citing work is using signal phrases, which leads to mentioning the author's name within the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 38). Furthermore, the chapter explains that a bibliography lists all work from where references are taken in a paper. Multiple formats can be followed to cite and populate the bibliography, depending on the source document type cited, such as a book, online documents, etc. (EUCLID 2024, 38).

As a Master in Public Health student, I have learned the concepts and practices of ethical academic writing. Later, as a researcher, writing research manuscripts ensured I mindfully employed the steps to avoid plagiarism. However, this coursework details the theoretical and practical aspects of plagiarism. I could again reflect on it and realize that this must be employed more mindfully in my daily practice of policy writing, research proposal formulations, and academic writing. While citing from published works seems straightforward when I adopt a pre-existing concept or benchmarking from a best practice, the mindfulness about citing the source may be noticed. This guideline has made me understand very concisely when and how this needs to be avoided

5) WRITING STYLES

The next section in the study material elaborates on the concept and methods of a style guide and the Chicago style of writing (EUCLID 2024, 40). A style guide aligns the writer's writing style with a particular publication guideline (EUCLID 2024, 40-57). While it is discussed in the document that there exist alternate schools of thought in creative writing around the fact that a good writer should not need a writing style guideline, it is emphasized that the role of a style guide is really to make one's writing more consistent (EUCLID 2024, 41).

Following a particular writing style is new to me as I have not been exposed to this theoretically before. However, while reading this course material, I can relate to my master's degree training, where this is taught differently. In my industry practice, writing health policy often requires a more contextual approach to the organization where the policy will be implemented. I have yet to explore whether sticking to a specific writing style will have its limitations in that setting. Regarding the aspects of writing discussed in the coursework, such as the layout, font, readership, terminology, structure, etc. (EUCLID 2024, 41). I completely relate to this as being very relevant in academic and industry-based writing. One of the prime focuses of health policy writing is standardization; by following a regimented structure, an organization's policies will be able to achieve the same.

6) CORRECTIONS AND FEEDBACK TO SUBMITTED PAPERS

The final section in the coursework elaborates on what to expect once a response paper is submitted. There is also a supplementary video on this topic as part of the coursework package. The concepts of tracking changes and inserting comments using the Microsoft Word features are elaborated with examples (EUCLID 2024, 66-71).

I have been using the track changes features in my professional practice for a long time and have benefited widely. I can see how this will be helpful for a student to understand not only the teacher's perspectives but also review their work in a line-by-line manner.

7) CONCLUSION

I am currently working to develop a project proposal on screening and early diagnosis of cancers in the catchment population of my hospital. While studying this course material, I could reflect on the steps of writing this program proposal, the importance of a thorough literature review, and even consider adopting a particular writing style. While industry-based writing often takes the liberty to be less conservative in its approach, the benefits of following a structured approach were very forthcoming from the study material of this period. I can adopt a few critical concepts learned here and implement them in my work as a policymaker.

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